

A geometrical model of the field-to-grid transformation

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Introduction

In two previous notes* I discussed the effects of a tilted and displaced grid on the transformation from field angles to grid coordinates. These studies were based on a very simple instrument model including only the effects of geometrical projection, as opposed to a full OTF calculation.

In the present note I return to basically the same model, but somewhat extended and reformulated in a way more suitable for numerical evaluation and fitting to 'real' data. It is found that most of the model parameters can be determined from the field-to-grid transformation obtained in the great-circle reduction. The fitted geometrical model is able to reproduce the observed transformation with an RMS error of a few mas. The model can thus be used as a tool for interpretation of at least certain terms of the field-to-grid transformation, and in particular of the temporal variations of this transformation. The model has also been used to extrapolate the main field geometry to the starmapper grid as a means of checking the in-orbit geometrical starmapper calibration.

Scope of the model

Before the model itself is described, its limited scope and applicability must be emphasized. The purpose of the model is *not* to give a precise physical 'explanation' of the field-to-grid transformation. Rather, it should be regarded as a tool for understanding to what extent the observed transformation can be attributed to simple geometry. For instance, the discovery of a sizeable 'differential grid rotation' in the first successful GCR was (I believe) a surprise to all of us, although it can be understood very simply as the result of a small displacement of the grid; thus it falls entirely within the scope of this model. On the other hand, effects such as the phase difference between the two harmonics or the chromatic terms of the field-to-grid transformation obviously cannot be explained by such a geometrical model.

Model parameters

The model assumes that all optical surfaces are perfect in shape but possibly displaced or tilted. Only one ray is traced, namely, the ray passing through the centre of curvature of the spherical mirror. Since we are thus considering a system with infinitely small aperture, we can also assume that the two segments of the beam combiner are flat. The imaging properties

* *Field-to-grid coordinate transformation for an idealised Schmidt telescope with tilted and displaced grid*, 1984 May 6 (erroneously dated one year earlier); and *Derivation of the starmapper geometry in field coordinates* (NDAC/LO/063), 1985 September 5

of such a system is invariant to a parallel shift of the beam combiner surfaces. It is then convenient to assume that both beam combiner surfaces contain the centre of curvature of the spherical mirror. Clearly the flat folding mirror can be disregarded in the model.

The position and orientation of optical elements are specified relative to a *laboratory coordinate system* $[X Y Z]$ with origin at the centre of curvature of the spherical mirror. The Z axis coincides with the intersection of the beam combiner surfaces, while X is the bisector of the mirror normals n_p (preceding) and n_f (following field). With Γ denoting twice the angle between the two normals, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} n_p &= X \cos(\Gamma/4) + Y \sin(\Gamma/4) \\ n_f &= X \cos(\Gamma/4) - Y \sin(\Gamma/4) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Note that $[X Y Z]$ is not quite the same as the instrument system $[x y z]$ (although they would coincide for a perfectly aligned instrument), nor is Γ quite equal to the basic angle γ .

The position and curvature of the spherical mirror do not enter as parameters of the model, since the centre of curvature is taken as origin and the radius of curvature has no influence on the geometrical image (cf. Figure 1).

Figure 1. For the definition of instrument geometry

We next define a *grid coordinate system* $[F G H]$ which is physically attached to the grid and measured in mm. The origin of the system is the nominal centre of the grid, halfway between the two reference marks. (G, H) are measured in the plane tangent to the grid at

the nominal centre. F is measured positive on the convex side of the grid. The slits are nominally delineated by straight lines in the (G, H) plane, with the 'vertical' and main grid slits parallel to the H axis.

The curvature radius of the grid, R , is formally a model parameter. However, computations show that one would need rather drastic changes in the curvature to produce a measurable distortion (some 2% for 1 mas distortion). Since the actual radius is probably very close to nominal, it is therefore better to consider $R = 1400$ mm as a fixed parameter. The coordinate F is then a known function of (G, H) , which we write in the computationally favourable form:

$$F = \frac{-(G^2 + H^2)}{R + \sqrt{R^2 - (G^2 + H^2)}} \equiv F(G, H) \quad (2)$$

The relation between laboratory coordinates and grid coordinates is defined by six parameters which specify the displacement and rotation necessary to bring a coordinate system initially aligned with $[X \ Y \ Z]$ into coincidence with $[F \ G \ H]$:

- displace the origin to (X_0, Y_0, Z_0) ;
- rotate an angle ψ about the 3rd axis;
- rotate an angle θ about the 2nd axis;
- rotate an angle ϕ about the 1st axis.

The resulting transformation is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} X_0 \\ Y_0 \\ Z_0 \end{pmatrix} + \mathbf{A} \begin{pmatrix} F \\ G \\ H \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} c\theta c\psi & s\phi s\theta c\psi - c\phi s\psi & c\phi s\theta c\psi + s\phi s\psi \\ c\theta s\psi & s\phi s\theta s\psi + c\phi c\psi & c\phi s\theta s\psi - s\phi c\psi \\ -s\theta & s\phi c\theta & c\phi c\theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Nominally, the slit centres of the main grid should be straight and equidistant lines in the (G, H) plane. Due to imperfections of the electron beam pattern generator, this is not strictly true for the actual grid. Part of the deviations are described by the small and medium scale irregularities, but here we are only concerned with large scale errors that may represent some kind of projection error. To this end we define an *EBPM coordinate system* $[f \ g \ h]$, which may be tilted with respect to $[F \ G \ H]$. The slits occupy their nominal positions in the (g, h) plane, apart from irregularities, and they are projected normally from this plane onto the grid surface. The tilt of the EBPG system with respect to the grid system is described by the two rotations needed to bring $[F \ G \ H]$ into coincidence with $[f \ g \ h]$:

- first, a rotation by the angle α about the 3rd axis;
- then, a rotation by the angle β about the 2nd axis.

This gives the transformation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} F \\ G \\ H \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c\beta c\alpha & -s\alpha & s\beta c\alpha \\ c\beta s\alpha & c\alpha & s\beta s\alpha \\ -s\beta & 0 & c\beta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f \\ g \\ h \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

In order to obtain a transformation from (g, h) to (G, H) one has to introduce the grid surface equation (2); the result can be obtained as the solution of a quadratic equation, or perhaps more conveniently by iterating the three equations:

$$G = g \cos \alpha - (F \sec \beta - g \sin \alpha + h \tan \beta) \tan \alpha \quad (6a)$$

$$H = h \cos \beta + (F \sec \beta - g \sin \alpha + h \tan \beta) \sin \beta + g \sin \beta \sin \alpha \quad (6b)$$

$$F = F(G, H) \quad (6c)$$

starting from $F = 0$. The inverse transformation from (G, H) to (g, h) is obtained directly from equations (2) and (5), noting that the inverse of the square matrix in (5) equals its transpose.

This completes the specification of the instrument model. The model parameters are: $\Gamma, R, X_0, Y_0, Z_0, \phi, \theta, \psi, \alpha$ and β . We have already noted that R should not be considered a free parameter. Also, it can be seen that Y_0 and ψ are coupled in the sense that displacing the grid along the $\mathbf{Y}$ axis is equivalent to a simultaneous rotation of the grid and beam combiner, each about its own $\mathbf{Z}$ axis, plus some second-order adjustment of the distance between the two elements. Since rotating the beam combiner about $\mathbf{Z}$ does not change the field-to-grid transformation, we conclude that Y_0 and ψ are, in effect, indistinguishable. Without loss of generality we can therefore set $\psi = 0$. Inspection of equation (5) shows, furthermore, that the EBPG tilt angle β does not enter the expression for g as a function of (F, G, H) . Hence it cannot be determined from the observed distortion of the main field, and we are forced to assume $\beta = 0$. The remaining seven parameters $(\Gamma, X_0, Y_0, Z_0, \phi, \theta, \alpha)$ can be adjusted freely to represent the observed field-to-grid transformation as closely as possible.

Ray tracing

In order to adjust the instrument parameters it is necessary to trace a number of rays through the instrument from several points in either field of view. Both forward and reverse tracing is required, and it is important that the numerical routines for doing this are stable and accurate. Only a few basic equations shall be given here.

Given the instrument parameters and the unit vector $\mathbf{u}$ towards a star, the direction of the ray after reflection in the beam combiner is given by:

$$\mathbf{v} = 2nn'\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{n}$ is the mirror normal from equation (1). The origin of $\mathbf{v}$ is the centre of curvature of the spherical mirror. After reflection in that mirror, the ray returns to the origin in direction $-\mathbf{v}$. Its intercept with the grid is computed from the parametric equation:

$$|\mathbf{v}t - \mathbf{c}| = R \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{c}$ is the position of the centre of curvature of the grid. The latter is obtained by setting $F = -R$ and $G = H = 0$ in equation (3). Solving t in equation (8) we find:

$$t = \mathbf{v}'\mathbf{c} + \sqrt{R^2 + (\mathbf{v}'\mathbf{c})^2 - \mathbf{c}'\mathbf{c}} \quad (9)$$

The point of interception is vt in the laboratory system; by means of equations (3) and (5) it can be transformed to the grid and EBPG systems, respectively, finally yielding the (g, h) coordinates of the ray.

Raytracing in the opposite direction, starting from the a point (g, h) in EBPG coordinates, is done by successively applying equations (6), (3) and (7). The result is a direction in space, expressed in the laboratory system, corresponding to the point (g, h) .

Relation to field coordinates

The laboratory system $[\mathbf{X} \ \mathbf{Y} \ \mathbf{Z}]$ is not directly available to measurements. Instead we have to define yet another coordinate frame, namely the *instrument system* $[\mathbf{x} \ \mathbf{y} \ \mathbf{z}]$ and the associated *field coordinates* (w, z) , to which the in-orbit calibrations can be related. These systems are defined by the optics together with a reference value γ_0 of the basic angle and two specific features on the grid:

- the chevron apex of the active starmapper, which defines the origin of the transverse field coordinate z , and
- the centre line of the main field, halfway between the 1344th and 1345th slits, which defines the origin of the longitudinal coordinate w .

In the instrument system, the direction in space corresponding to field coordinates (w, z) is:

$$\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{x} \ \mathbf{y} \ \mathbf{z}] \begin{pmatrix} \mp w \sin(\gamma_0/2) + \sqrt{1 - w^2 - z^2} \cos(\gamma_0/2) \\ +w \cos(\gamma_0/2) \pm \sqrt{1 - w^2 - z^2} \sin(\gamma_0/2) \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where upper/lower sign refers to the preceding/following field. To establish a relation with the laboratory system we need to specify the reference basic angle γ_0 , the EBPG coordinates of the starmapper apex (g_A, h_A) , and the centre line of the main field in EBPG coordinates, $g = g_0(h)$. (In practice it will be assumed that $h_A = 0$ and $g_0 \equiv 0$, so that only γ_0 and g_A have to be specified.) The procedure to calculate $[\mathbf{x} \ \mathbf{y} \ \mathbf{z}]$ in the laboratory system is then as follows.

A ray from (g_A, h_A) is traced through the preceding field. Let $\mathbf{a}_p$ be the resulting unit vector towards the point on the sky that is imaged on the starmapper apex. Similarly trace out the corresponding direction $\mathbf{a}_f$ through the following field. Then:

$$\mathbf{z} = \langle \mathbf{a}_f \times \mathbf{a}_p \rangle \quad (11)$$

with $\langle \rangle$ denoting vector normalization.

It is now necessary to find the two directions $\mathbf{0}_p$ and $\mathbf{0}_f$, perpendicular to $\mathbf{z}$, which are imaged onto a point satisfying the main field centre line equation $g = g_0(h)$. In my routines this is done by a rather crude iterative procedure. Consider for instance the preceding field. The auxiliary unit vector $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{a}_p$ is first computed. Candidate solution vectors are now parametrized as $\langle \mathbf{a}_p + \mathbf{q}s \rangle$, where s is a scalar to be determined. The EBPG position (g, h) corresponding to an arbitrary value of s can be obtained by raytracing. By inverse linear interpolation we easily find the value s_p (say) satisfying the equation $g - g_0(h) = 0$. Then $\mathbf{0}_p = \langle \mathbf{a}_p + \mathbf{q}s_p \rangle$. The calculation of $\mathbf{0}_f$ is analogous.

Given the viewing directions $\mathbf{0}_p$ and $\mathbf{0}_f$ the remaining instrument axes are finally obtained as:

$$\mathbf{x} = \langle \mathbf{0}_p + \mathbf{0}_f \rangle \quad (12a)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{x} \quad (12b)$$

The actual basic angle (not a free parameter!) is:

$$\gamma = \arccos(\mathbf{0}'_p \mathbf{0}_f) \quad (13)$$

Note that the field coordinates of the arbitrary star direction $\mathbf{u}$ are obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} w &= \mathbf{y}'\mathbf{u} \cos(\gamma_0/2) \mp \mathbf{x}'\mathbf{u} \sin(\gamma_0/2) \\ z &= \mathbf{z}'\mathbf{u} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Model adjustment

Stellar observations on the main grid provide a determination of the longitudinal EBPG coordinate g as function of time. The basic assumption is that g increments by exactly $8.2 \mu\text{m}$ for each modulation period. (This is in fact the ruler from which all linear dimensions are derived.) In the great-circle reduction such observations are combined to establish an empirical relation between g and the field coordinates (w, z) . The relation is expressed in the form of polynomial coefficients g_{ij} , h_{ij} in the (simplified) field-to-grid transformation formula:

$$g = -F_0 w + \sum_{i,j} (g_{ij} \pm h_{ij}) w^i z^j \quad (15)$$

F_0 is a reference value for the equivalent focal length. Usually terms up to 4th order ($i+j < 4$) are included. The complete field-to-grid transformation may contain also chromatic and temporal terms, but they are not considered here.

Given the coefficients g_{ij} , h_{ij} from the great-circle reduction and the corresponding reference values γ_0 , F_0 we are thus able to compute the 'observed' EBPG coordinate g_O for arbitrary position (w, z) in either field of view. The geometrical instrument model described above yields, on the other hand, the 'calculated' coordinate g_C of the same field position. This value depends on the model parameters, which are now adjusted to minimize the mean square deviation in both fields:

$$\text{RMS}^2 = \frac{1}{2n^2} \sum_{\text{FOV}_s} \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^n [g_O(w_k, z_j) - g_C(w_k, z_l)]^2 \quad (16)$$

A total of 98 rays ($n = 7$) is used, with a discretization step of 0.0022 in w and z . The adjustment of the seven 'free' model parameters is made with a standard minimization routine not requiring the calculation of derivatives (E04FDF from the NAG library). Double precision is used throughout.

A numerical example

The model was first applied to the great-circle reduction data obtained in Copenhagen for Comparison set #1 (observed on December 9, 1989; instrument parameters taken from Petersen's e-mail of August 20, 1990). Reference values are $\gamma_0 = 1.012436410$ ($58^\circ 29.999946''$) and $F_0 = 1400.141882$ mm (170749.010 slits/radian). The relevant instrument parameters are shown in Table 1. They are expressed in milli-arcsec per Φ^{i+j} , where $\Phi = \sin 0.45^\circ$.

Table 1 Instrument parameters for Comparison set #1

i	j	g_{ij}	h_{ij}
0	0	—	626.309
1	0	-853.250	-3.216
0	1	-2607.569	178.487
2	0	-3.658	-1.775
1	1	-1.209	-0.641
0	2	-6.192	0.306
3	0	-4.410	—
2	1	-2.551	—
1	2	-6.808	—
0	3	-3.139	—

The starmapper apex coordinate was set to its nominal value, $g_A = -21.63385$ mm (Vol. III, Figure 1.11). Adjustment of the model parameters gave the values shown in Table 2. The RMS residual was 2.24 mas; individual residuals for all 98 rays are shown in Table 3.

Table 2 Model parameters adjusted to the data in Table 1

Parameter	Value	
Γ	1.01244249170	rad
X_0	1400.88504	mm
Y_0	0.27976	mm
Z_0	0.31311	mm
ϕ	331.53	arcsec
θ	-65.74	arcsec
α	159.43	arcsec
γ	1.01244247530	rad

Table 3 Residuals $g_O - g_C$ (in mas) versus position in field (w, z) (in mrad)

$z \setminus w$	-6.6	-4.4	-2.2	0.0	2.2	4.4	6.6	
-6.6	2.7	-0.1	-1.1	-0.9	-0.1	0.7	1.0	
-4.4	-0.8	-2.4	-2.5	-1.4	0.1	1.6	2.4	
-2.2	-2.5	-3.4	-2.7	-1.1	0.9	2.7	3.7	
0.0	-2.9	-3.3	-2.3	-0.4	1.7	3.5	4.5	F-field
2.2	-2.5	-2.7	-1.7	0.2	2.2	3.7	4.3	
4.4	-1.6	-2.0	-1.2	0.3	1.9	2.8	2.7	
6.6	-0.8	-1.6	-1.3	-0.4	0.4	0.5	-0.6	
-6.6	5.6	2.8	1.3	0.4	-0.4	-1.7	-4.2	
-4.4	2.2	0.4	-0.2	-0.3	-0.5	-1.3	-3.3	
-2.2	0.6	-0.4	-0.5	-0.2	0.0	-0.5	-2.5	
0.0	0.4	-0.3	-0.1	0.5	0.7	0.1	-2.0	P-field
2.2	1.2	0.6	0.8	1.1	1.1	0.1	-2.5	
4.4	2.5	1.7	1.5	1.4	0.8	-0.8	-4.2	
6.6	3.9	2.6	1.8	0.9	-0.5	-3.2	-7.6	

It is instructive to see which terms g_{ij}, h_{ij} the model is able to adjust to. Table 4 gives the instrument parameters obtained by fitting equation (14) to the computed coordinates g_C . The only terms that attain significant values in the model are: h_{00} (basic angle), g_{10} (scale value), g_{01} (grid rotation about the optical axis), h_{01} (differential grid rotation), and the tilt terms g_{20}, g_{11}, g_{02} . The model is incapable of reproducing the remaining terms, such as h_{10} (differential scale) and all cubic terms ($i + j = 3$). (Part of the cubic terms are absorbed by the correlated linear terms, which probably explains why the fitted values of g_{10} and g_{01} differ by a few mas from the observed coefficients. Similarly the observed h_{20} , which the model cannot produce, is partly absorbed by the model's h_{00} .) The pattern of residuals in Table 3 is largely explained by the cubic terms and differential scale value.

A remark: The observed g_{30} and g_{12} could to a large extent be 'explained' if we allowed the curvature of the grid to change. The required radius is nearly $R = 1600$ mm, however, which seems absurd. Perhaps some feature of the EBPG hardware could produce a similar distortion, i.e. of the form $(w^2 + z^2)w$? I return to the cubic terms in a later section.

Table 4 Instrument parameters for the adjusted model

i	j	g_{ij}	h_{ij}
0	0	—	625.861
1	0	-857.850	-0.258
0	1	-2610.106	178.493
2	0	-3.652	-0.020
1	1	-1.207	-0.002
0	2	-6.194	-0.020
3	0	0.033	0.001
2	1	0.001	-0.002
1	2	0.031	-0.001
0	3	-0.005	0.002

Derivation of the starmapper geometry

Given the adjusted instrument model, it is easy to derive the (nominal) starmapper geometry in (w, z) coordinates. Adopting $g = -13.13005$ mm for the reference line of the vertical slits and $g = -21.63385 + |h|$ for the chevron, a number of rays were traced from points on the reference lines through both fields. Quadratic polynomials in z were then fitted to the resulting field coordinates. The RMS residual of the fit was less than 10^{-8} arcsec. The following equations for the starmapper reference lines were thus derived (the reference basic angle for these date is 1.012442471 rad):

- Vertical slits:

$$w = \begin{cases} 0.009372669 - 0.001501085z - 0.000483571z^2, & \text{P-field} \\ 0.009372669 - 0.001721327z - 0.000483569z^2, & \text{F-field} \end{cases} \quad (14a)$$

- Chevron slits, $z > 0$:

$$w = \begin{cases} 0.015442938 - 1.002996365z - 0.000848155z^2, & \text{P-field} \\ 0.015442940 - 1.003438319z - 0.000845293z^2, & \text{F-field} \end{cases} \quad (14b)$$

- Chevron slits, $z < 0$:

$$w = \begin{cases} 0.015442938 + 0.996989043z - 0.001077030z^2, & \text{P-field} \\ 0.015442940 + 0.996549929z - 0.001079702z^2, & \text{F-field} \end{cases} \quad (14c)$$

I have compared this result with the empirical starmapper calibration made at RGO (van Leeuwen, e-mail of 1990 Oct 22) and with the FAST/SRU calibration based on an extrapolation of the main field distortion (Schrijver, e-mail of 1990 Oct 9, with ground-based MSI removed from the chevron data). Figure 2 shows the differences $g_{\text{SRU}} - g_{\text{LO}}$ (crosses) and $g_{\text{RGO}} - g_{\text{LO}}$ (solid curves) as functions of h . The straight vertical lines at position 0 represent

the geometry according to equation (14). The systematic shifts in g between the different calibrations is of no real significance, since it can be compensated by a corresponding shift of the abscissas. What matters are differences in slope and shape, and these are typically less than 20 mas RMS. I consider this a rather satisfactory agreement, particularly in view of the variety of methods involved. The curvature of the FAST data compared with RGO and LO, as well as the cusp at the chevron apex, may be due to the extrapolation of cubic terms in the SRU calibration.

Temporal evolution of the model parameters

The geometrical instrument model was fitted to the results of 33 great-circle reductions performed at SRU (Schrijver, e-mail of 1990 Nov 2). Figure 3 shows the fitted model parameters as functions of time. A few comments:

- *The beam-combiner angle Γ .* The evolution is practically the same as for the basic angle (γ).
- *The grid position X_0 .* During the first few months of 1990, this parameter decreased by about 3 μm . After that it appears to have settled around $X_0 = 1400.8833$ mm. The ensuing variations with a peak-to-peak amplitude of about 2 μm are probably real and related to the refocussings. Cf. the vertical bars on top of Figure 3b which indicate the instants of refocussing, usually by +2 steps or 2.76 μm nominally. Interpretation of X_0 is a bit tricky because it must be remembered that, on one hand, it is basically derived from the scale value (g_{10}) while, on the other hand, it represents the distance from the centre of curvature of the spherical mirror to the grid. We can assume that the grid is (on the average) kept at the optimal focus, or halfway between the spherical mirror and the centre of curvature. It follows that X_0 equals the distance from the spherical mirror to the grid – but only at the instants when the instrument is optimally focussed. The variations in Figure 3b can then be understood as follows. During the first months of 1990, the actual focal length of the instrument (equal to the mirror-grid distance at optimal focus) decreased by a few microns. This must be due to a physical deformation of one of the mirrors (the spherical mirror, the flat folding mirror, or the beam combiner) changing the total power of the optical system. The required deformation is of the order of 30 nm peak value. After that, the focal length has remained constant at 1400.8833 mm. That frequent refocussing is needed also *after* the first few months indicates that it is now mainly the *structure* that is changing. In particular it appears that the structure connecting the spherical and flat mirrors is steadily shrinking, thus increasing the apparent focal length (scale) while moving the grid out of focus. This process is compensated by the periodic refocussing moving the grid away from the flat mirror. This sense of direction of the changes is consistent with the information in ESTEC.STATUS.11/6.
- *Longitudinal grid position Y_0 .* This parameter is not well determined and I believe that most of the variations seen in Figure 3c are noise. In any case there is no evidence of any secular trend in Y_0 .
- *Transverse grid position Z_0 .* This parameter, which generates the ‘differential grid rotation’ (h_{01}), is well determined and shows a very clear and steady evolution (Figure 3d). Recall that Z_0 is the position of the grid centre above the plane defined by the beam

combiner normals. The variation is perhaps most easily understood as a rotation of the beam combiner about the Y axis relative to the other optical parts.

- *Grid orientation about the optical axis (ϕ) and Y axis (θ).* The evolution is clear and steady in both parameters (Figure 3e-f).
- *Electron beam inclination α .* This parameter is not very well determined and the variations in Figure 3g are probably not real. No trend can be discerned. In theory we would not expect this parameter to change, since it is part of the supposedly fixed slit pattern.

Figure 3h shows the RMS residual of the model fit as a function of time. In a sense this is perhaps the most remarkable result of the present study, namely, that the fit gets worse all the time. At the beginning of the mission the geometrical model could 'explain' almost the whole observed field-to-grid transformation. But after less than a year the residuals are 2 or 3 times larger. Closer examination shows that a large part of this is due to the differential scale value h_{10} , which the geometrical model cannot reproduce. Figure 4 shows how the scale correction has evolved quite differently in the two fields of view. Extrapolating backwards in time it would appear that the differential scale was practically zero at about the time of launch. A smaller part of the increased RMS residual is due to the cubic terms of the field-to-grid transformation, which tend to increase in absolute values (Figure 5).

The evolution of the differential scale and cubic terms can only be understood in terms of rather complicated deformations of one or several of the mirrors. For instance, to produce a cubic distortion in the field seems to require a quartic deformation of a mirror which is not in the plane of the entrance pupil, that is, of the folding or spherical mirror. The required deformation is of the order of 50 nm peak value. The corresponding RMS wavefront error would be of the order of $\lambda/30$, hardly enough to decrease the modulation by a significant amount. However, if it continues to grow almost linearly with time, as suggested by some of the diagrams, then the effect on M_1 and M_2 could eventually become important.

Conclusions

The geometrical model has proved useful as a means of understanding certain aspects of the Hipparcos instrument. In particular the temporal evolution of the instrument is probably better followed in terms of the present model parameters than the various terms of the field-to-grid transformation. Perhaps even more important is to see what the model *cannot* explain, and what must therefore be attributed to surface deformation.

I intend to apply this model to the results of all NDAC great-circle reductions transferred to Lund. With 20 times higher time resolution than in the present study, some new insight into the instrument is likely to be gained.

Figure 2 Comparing the starmapper geometric calibrations of SRU (crosses) and RGO (solid curves). The loci of the starmapper reference lines are shown relative to the position derived from the geometric instrument model.

Figure 3a-d Evolution of geometric instrument parameters Γ , X_0 , Y_0 , Z_0 from fits to the 33 first-look great-circle reductions.

Figure 3e-h Evolution of geometric instrument parameters ϕ , θ , α and the RMS residual of the model fits.

Figure 4 Evolution of the scale correction for the preceding field ($g_{10} + h_{10}$, solid curve) and following field ($g_{10} - h_{10}$, dotted curve). The reference scale corresponds to a slit period of exactly 1.208 arcsec.

Figure 5 Evolution of the cubic terms of the field-to-grid transformation in the preceding (solid) and following field (dotted).